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Specific activation of CDH11 in glioblastoma.

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Activation of CDH11 is specific, because cadherins CDH8, CDH9, CDH12, CDH13, CDH18 and CDH22 are differentially expressed but repressed.

Keywords: CDH11, endothelial cell adhesion molecule, glioblastoma, systems biology of glioblastoma, targeted therapeutics in glioblastoma.

1 Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults
2 including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted
3 therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of
4 fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated
5 with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total
6 transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human
7 glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint
8 of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe
9 here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole
10 transcriptome methods.

11 **Methods**

12 We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene
13 expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods
14 (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip
15 technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the
16 analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq
17 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma
18 tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. The Benjamini and Hochberg method
19 of p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess
20 statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and
21 the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional
22 co-regulation studies (8).

23 **Results**

24 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6)
25 to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression
26 features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

27 CDH11 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

28 1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1672611	9.99E-09	-7.1351638	9.84933	-1.54616358	CDH11	1493/47229	96.8

29 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
30 tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of cadherin 11, encoded by CDH11 in glioblastoma
31 in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of CDH11 changed more than 95% of the human brain and
32 brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case,
33 47,229 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of
34 *CDH11* messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CDH11 during
35 transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

$n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1009	2.06E-03	0.374	-3.0811758	-1.15352893	797.16	CDH11	2637/19678	86.6

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CDH11 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of CDH11 here changed more than 85% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CDH11 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CDH11 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

Thus, CDH11 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the glioblastoma subtype in humans.

CDH11 transcriptional co-regulation.

Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

In the transformed brain, CDH11 was transcriptionally co-regulated with fibronectin 1 (*FN1*), a recurrently differentially expressed tumor protein, *ADAM9*, a metalloprotease that functions at the extracellular matrix and dermatan sulfate epimerase (*DSE*), an enzyme functioning in synthesis of dermatan sulfate, important for CNS development.

1 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
2 CDH11 as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level query
3 into CDH11 molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its co-regulation
4 with FN1, ADAM9 and DSE.

4 **Discussion**

5 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
6 endothelial cell adhesion molecule, CDH11, was among the genes most differentially expressed in the
7 primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; CDH11 was expressed at significantly higher levels in
8 glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. CDH11 is a target of interest for rationally designed
9 medical treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
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Supplemental data

Figure S1: CDH11 activation is specific because cadherins CDH8, CDH9, CDH12, CDH13, CDH18 and CDH22 are differentially expressed but repressed.

CDH8

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1757020	1.18E-14	11.6471808	23.249796	1.34887651	CDH8	71/47229	99.8

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1006	6.10E-04	0.867	3.4271655	2.97015101	320.72	CDH8	2086/19678	89.4

CDH9

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1675454	3.89E-08	6.7196543	8.512027	0.46775757	CDH9	1920/47229	95.9

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1007	3.32E-13	0.958	7.2806661	6.9779913	111.19	CDH9	227/19678	98.8

CDH12

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1709269	6.45E-09	7.2695657	10.280007	1.66299916	CDH12	1393/47229	97.1

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1010	2.32E-07	0.88	5.1718956	4.55130436	39.17	CDH12	728/47229	98.5

CDH13

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1766925	5.04E-07	5.9413315	5.997276	1.51410335	CDH13	2940/47229	93.8

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1012	2.39E-07	0.652	5.1658565	3.367388	505.42	CDH13	732/19678	96.3

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CDH18

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
ILMN_1733669	1.53E-10	8.4368016	13.959804	2.25634374	CDH18	692/47229	98.5

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
1016	4.62E-07	0.905	5.0414353	4.5604412	193.41	CDH18	799/19678	95.9

CDH22

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>B</u>	<u>logFC</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
ILMN_1753586	3.97E-10	8.1357926	13.023004	1.06364567	CDH22	823/47229	98.3

<u>ID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
64405	7.85E-22	0.583	9.601897	5.60135043	309.37	CDH22	76/19678	99.6